

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D6.2: Processing techniques

WP6: Implementation of new interfaces and methodologies in
coastal systems

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Glossary and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BC	Brockmann Consult
BGC	Biogeochemical
CF	Climate Forecast (Convention for NetCDF)
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNR	National Research Council (Italy)
CRPS	Continuous Ranked Probability Score
CROCO	Coastal and Regional Ocean COmmunity model
DCSM-FM	Delft3D Coastal Systems Model - Flexible Mesh
DPV	Data Product Validation
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
DCSM	Delft3D Coastal Systems Model
EO	Earth Observation
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ESC	Environmental and Societal Challenges
FRM	Fiducial Reference Measurements
FOCCUS	Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean for Copernicus users
GLO4ens	Global Ocean Physics Ensemble Reanalysis
HABs	Harmful Algal Blooms
HEREON	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon
HR	High-Resolution
HFR	High-Frequency Radar
IFREMER	French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea
ISAR	Infrared Sea surface temperature Autonomous Radiometer
MET.NO	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
MHWs	Marine Heatwaves
MHD	Marine Hydrographic Directorate (Romania)
MSCS	Member State Coastal System
MSI	MultiSpectral Instrument
NERSC	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (Norway)
MSCS	Member State Coastal Systems
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NOC	National Oceanography Centre (UK)
NW	North West
ODP	Operational Data Product
OGCM	Ocean Global Circulation Model
OLCI	Ocean and Land Colour Instrument
PDPD	Proof of concept Data Product
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
PU	Public
PUM	Product User Manual
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROFI	Region Of Freshwater Influence
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
RBINS	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
S2	Sentinel-2
S3	Sentinel-3
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SAV	Submerged Aquatic Vegetation
SCHISM	Semi-implicit Cross-scale Hydrosience Integrated System Model

SDB	Satellite-Derived Bathymetry
SCHISM	Semi-implicit Cross-scale Hydrosience Integrated System Model
SHOM	Service Hydrographique et Océanographique de la Marine (France)
SLA	Sea Level Anomaly
SOCIB	Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System
SPM	Suspended Particulate Matter
SRResNet	Super-Resolution RESidual NETwork
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
SWH	Significant Wave Height
SWOT	Surface Water and Ocean Topography
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TWL	Total Water level
WMOP	Western Mediterranean OPerational forecasting system
WP	Work Package
WW3	WaveWatch III®
XBEACH	Cross-shore Beach Dynamics Model

1. Executive summary

The **FOCCUS** project (<https://foccus-project.eu/>) aims to enhance coastal ocean observation and forecasting for Copernicus users by designing and implementing a range of high-resolution data products. This short report is meant to provide a software repository of algorithms, developed under Tasks 6.2 and 6.3, which involve implementing new modeling techniques (AI and probabilistic approaches) and optimizing integrated systems. It also aims to complement milestones MS6.2 "Nested models implemented in a unified framework" and MS6.3 "New observation operators", as well as deliverable D6.2 "Processing techniques", which is associated with tasks 6.2 and 6.3. The milestones and the deliverable are software and/or data, and demonstrated through codes or data that are accessible via the project space on Zenodo or similar open systems. Brief descriptions of the work are given here to provide context, along with a complete list of the software/data delivered (with links).

Not all MCSCs are represented in this work. For a description of the MCSCs we refer to the Section 2 of D6.1 report "Overview of Member State Coastal Systems (MCSC)", which contains a complete list. All software is listed in [Table 4.1](#), and are referred to in the text according to their position in this table.

2. New modelling techniques

2.1 Ensemble techniques

Ensemble techniques are used to quantify uncertainties in ocean state forecasts. First initiated in the atmospheric community in the 1990's (<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/about/media-centre/focus/2017/fact-sheet-ensemble-weather-forecasting>), these techniques have recently emerged in the oceanic community, and this project aims at contributing to this effort. Ensemble techniques consist in producing multiple realizations of the same operational forecast system, each realization only differing in pre-defined metrics of the model (e.g. initial conditions, external forcing, model parameters) depending on the type of uncertainty we aim at quantifying (cf. below). Analyzing the different possible trajectories so produced inform us on possible future ocean states, offering a probabilistic view of the ocean dynamics and prediction errors.

Forecast uncertainties are usually clustered in three main types¹, accounting for uncertainties in external forcing (e.g. atmospheric conditions, open boundaries and river discharges; **Type I**), uncertainties in initial conditions (**Type II**) and uncertainties associated with numerical model imperfections (**Type III**). The latter two types are subdivided into: **Type IIa**, associated with small scale, uncorrelated *microscopic* uncertainties in initial conditions, representing the irreducible component of the non-linear, chaotic dynamics of the ocean; **Type IIb** associated with spatially organized *macroscopic* uncertainties in initial conditions, representing our imperfect knowledge of oceanic state at a given time; **Type IIIa** associated with *model inadequacy*, reflecting uncertainties in the reproduction of past observation; and **Type IIIb** associated with *model uncertainty*, which includes both uncertainties in the parameters values of the various parameterizations used within a given model, and uncertainties across different state-of-the-art models (e.g. ensemble of opportunity).

In FOCCUS subtask 6.2.1, progress on ensemble techniques involve sources of uncertainties classified as **Type I**, **Type IIa**, and **Type IIIb**. These three types of uncertainties have been identified as critical for the different case studies under consideration, including river plumes dynamics, surface drift, wave modelling and wave forecasting. Although these case studies are not all associated with applications detailed in Deliverable D8.1, we envision they will significantly push forward such applications and bring further understanding of potential forecast errors. Note that the ensemble of opportunity approach taken by **DMI** differs from other approaches as it involves a multi-model strategy while others are applied to a single model. These efforts are summarized below.

- **Type I:**
 - **RBINS:** We aim at identifying the respective role of uncertainties in i) atmospheric forcings, ii) land discharges, and iii) boundary conditions in determining the position of river plumes in the southern North Sea. Atmospheric perturbations correspond to the ensemble members of the ECMWF ERA5 ensemble. Land discharges perturbations are reconstructed following a time-series analysis for 85 rivers within our computational domain. A 180-day low pass filter is applied, river per river, to maintain the main trends, while the high-frequency anomalies with respect to this trend are resampled (assuming no temporal correlations). Perturbations of the ocean boundary conditions are obtained by applying the atmospheric perturbations to the larger (North Atlantic) domain used to generate the boundary forcings. The different ensembles will be compared in terms of spread for physical fields (surface temperature, salinity, and current velocities, potential energy anomaly). Following our focus on river plume dynamics, detailed assessments will be based on near-shore surface salinity observations, and aim at characterizing the consistency of the ensembles' spread using the continuous rank probability score (CRPS). Finally, maps of river plume presence likelihood, enabled by this new ensemble approach will be provided.
 - **SHOM:** We have interfaced our MSCS with the Global Ocean Physics Ensemble Reanalysis (GLO4ens) reported in Deliverable 6.1.

- **Type IIa**
 - **SHOM:** We have completed the implementation of stochastic modelling capabilities in the CROCO modelling platform, where 2D and 3D stochastic fields are generated on the native model grid through auto-regressive processes². *Micro* initial conditions ensembles are currently produced thanks to this new modelling capabilities. With these ensembles, we aim at quantifying uncertainties in surface currents associated with ocean turbulence and its feedback on air-sea momentum exchanges, respectively, for application to the case of surface drift (e.g. oil slicks) forecasts. The metrics used to assess the performance of this new modelling technique will thus focus on surface currents magnitude and direction with probabilistic approaches (e.g. ensemble mean and spread, continuous rank probability score (CRPS)).

- **Type IIIb:**
 - **CMCC:** We have defined, implemented, and finalized stochastic modelling capabilities for waves at the AdriFS MSCS. Our approach is based on a perturbed ensemble using the air-sea exchange parameter, in order to capture the variability

and uncertainty introduced by the parameterization of the source term inputs in the wave model. The ensemble consists of 12 members, and the outputs include the ensemble mean, selected percentiles, and spread for the variables Significant Wave Height and Mean Wave Period. Model performance will be assessed using metrics such as RMSE, bias, and correlation computed on the ensemble mean of Significant Wave Height, while the Continuous Ranked Probability Score (CRPS) will be used to evaluate the quality of the associated probabilistic distribution.

- **DMI:** The purpose of this study is to provide better pan-European Sea wave forecasts than existing products, i.e., CMEMS forecasts and national forecasts. A base study of this work is to validate the existing CMEMS and national wave forecasts, which has been carried out in phase-1. By aggregating CMEMS and national wave forecasts with satellite wave observations, a weighted, multi-model, pan-European Sea real-time wave forecast system has been developed. The preliminary results show improved forecasts compared to the existing ones. However, the weight calculation method needs further optimization, which will be made in phase 2.
- **SHOM:** We have completed the implementation of stochastic modelling capabilities in the CROCO modelling platform, where 2D and 3D stochastic fields are generated on the native model grid through auto-regressive processes². An Air-sea exchange parameter perturbed ensemble is currently produced thanks to this new modelling capabilities.

With this ensemble, we aim at quantifying uncertainties in surface currents associated with ocean turbulence and its feedback on air-sea momentum exchanges, respectively, for application to the case of surface drift (e.g. oil slicks) forecasts. The metrics used to assess the performance of this new modelling technique will thus focus on surface currents magnitude and direction with probabilistic approaches (e.g. ensemble mean and spread, continuous rank probability score (CRPS)).

2.2 AI techniques

Within the FOCCUS project, advanced AI techniques (including ConvLSTM, CGAN, SRResNet, ensemble SRResNet, MLR) are being developed and applied to enhance ocean forecasting capabilities, particularly in improving:

1) prediction of suspended sediment plumes:

- **Deltares** has developed a machine learning model that predicts suspended sediment plumes in the Rhine Region of Freshwater Influence, in the southern North Sea. The ConvLSTM machine learning model, which combines a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Long Short-Term Model (LSTM), was used for this. This model structure was optimised, and trained, validated and tested on one year of daily 3D DCSM-FM hydrodynamic output features (water level, currents, salinity, temperature) with a resolution of ~ 1 km x ~ 1 km and Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) observations from the Global Ocean Colour Bio-Geo-Chemical CMEMS product. The SPM output from the 3D DCSM-FM model, with sediment transport processes enabled, was taken as ground truth data. This has resulted in a machine learning model that can predict SPM fields from hydrodynamic data and satellite SPM observations, for 5 days in the future. The algorithm is available on a GitHub repository and through Zenodo (see section 4, *software #4*).

2) downscaling and super-resolution of ocean fields:

- **NERSC** has implemented a machine learning approach to downscale DUACS (<https://duacs.cls.fr/>) Surface height fields. The approach uses a Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (CGAN) and is trained on SWOT data from the first part of 2023. It uses independent SWOT data from the end of 2023 for validation. The super-resolution is done over the Lofoten basin on smaller patches of size 1000 km x 1000 km that are reassembled to reconstruct the full image. The results show that small scales corresponding to SWOT data can be reconstructed. The algorithm is available on a GitHub repository (see section 4, *software #7*)
- **Hereon** applied Super-Resolution Residual Network (SRResNet; see section 4, *software #1*) to downscale the ocean fields including sea surface height and currents in a coastal region of German Bight. High-resolution data from the numerical model SCHISM (Semi-implicit Cross-scale Hydroscience Integrated System Model) and the downsampled data were used for training and testing. The resolution of these ocean fields was enhanced from tens of kilometers to hundreds of meters, with a downscaling factor reaching up to 64. The model also shows good performance when directly using CMEMS data as low-resolution input and high-resolution SCHISM model results as target. Furthermore, an ensemble SRResNet (see section 4, *software #2*) and multivariate linear regression (MLR; see section 4, *software #3*) have been applied to do both self-variable (wave to wave) and cross-variable (wind to wave) spatial wave downscaling in the Black Sea. ERA5 data was used as low-resolution input and CMEMS data was used as target. The ensemble method simply averages the predictions from multiple trained epochs, which is generic and easy to be applied to models based on neural networks. This method significantly reduces the prediction instability of the base SRResNet model and the global errors. The ensemble SRResNet performs well in both self-variable and cross-variable spatial downscaling of significant wave height (SWH), while MLR performs well in self-variable downscaling.

The development of AI techniques in WP6 have created synergies with other partners in the project, in particular MET Norway with the development of coastal oceanic models driven by AI and SMHI for the downscaling applications. Additionally, AI-based techniques have also been used to implement interface improvements between CMEMS and MSCSs. An example of this is the use of a 4DVarNet-dLSTM model to gap fill SPM satellite observations. These techniques are further described in D6.1.

3. Optimisation of integrated systems

The work here is associated with the challenge of obtaining a seamless description of the coastal ocean from the land to the open ocean, and the optimal use of coastal observations. The coastal ocean dynamics is typically associated with strong riverine forcing, with complex water transformation processes and large contrasts in water mass properties over short temporal and spatial time scales. The work in T6.3 is divided into subtasks T6.3.1 synergistic use of models and observations (data assimilation), and T6.3.2 coastal-open ocean coupling (diagnostics).

3.1 Synergistic use of models and observations

Work in this task is concentrated in three main regions, each leveraging specific MSCS and observational data for synergistic model-observation use and multi-platform data assimilation:

- the Norwegian shelf seas, with the work done using the MSCS "Norkyst". Assimilation of in situ salinity/temperature, satellite SST, and HF radar radials using "Norkyst", with dedicated impact studies using the ROMS-4DVAR. Methods include assessments of observation errors used in the 4D-Var for tuning the system. Also, assessment of SAR Doppler data from WP2 for potential inclusion in DA (from T2.2.2 "sea level and currents"³), using the observation operator for radial velocity observations developed for HF radar (MET.NO).
- the Western-Mediterranean Sea, with work done using the SOCIB MSCS "WMOP": Enhance the forecasting performance of the [WMOP](https://www.socib.es/es/que-hacemos/prediccion-del-oceano) (<https://www.socib.es/es/que-hacemos/prediccion-del-oceano>) system by assimilating multi-platform observational data. A key focus is the integration of high-resolution Sea Surface Height data for coastal applications, obtained from Level-3 satellite altimetry from [Sentinel-6A-HR-20Hz](https://zenodo.org/records/14938132)⁴ (<https://zenodo.org/records/14938132>) from WP2. The current configuration of WMOP delivers 72-hour forecasts, assimilating data from sea level anomaly (SLA), Sea Surface Temperature (SST), high-frequency radar from the Ibiza Channel, S/T profiles from Argo floats, and mooring observations, using an Ensemble Optimal Interpolation data assimilation scheme (SOCIB).
- the Adriatic Sea (Mediterranean Sea) with the work done for MSCS AdriFS: Assimilation of salinity/temperature profiles and satellite sea-level anomaly observations into AdriFS. This involves coupling of the OceanVar variational data assimilation scheme developed at CMCC to the SHYFEM-MPI unstructured mesh ocean model. The OceanVar software is well-established for the global and regional modelling systems using structured grids, and its generalisation to unstructured grids will bring state-of-the-art assimilation methods to the AdriFS system (CMCC).

3.2 Coastal-open ocean coupling

The transient coastal ocean dynamics are challenging to model, and diagnostic tools need to be designed not only to provide information about model quality from core model variable statistics, but also quantitative information about derived parameters that give more insight into the strengths and weaknesses in the model functionality and input data. Examples of such derived parameters include freshwater height, potential energy anomalies, density ratios, and so on. Open source processing scripts are provided for the MSCS "Norkyst", which is extensively used for support of the blue economy in Norway.

- Front detection algorithms based on JUNO (<https://github.com/CoLAB-ATLANTIC/JUNO>) have been implemented for the MSCS "Norkyst", aiding the analysis of the baroclinic dynamics. These algorithms are primarily intended to assess the impacts of river runoff in the transition zone between the more topographically restricted fjord environment and the eddy-rich continental shelf (MET.NO, +ATLANTIC).
- Enhance land-ocean and coastal-offshore interactions and fluxes by complementing the unstructured SHYFEM model application with nudging of CMEMS temperature and salinity fields. In the nudging approach, a new source term is added to the prognostic equations that drag the results vs. the CMEMS values. Therefore, it uses dynamical relaxation of the equations to tend to the CMEMS values. The value of the relaxation coefficient is spatially varying over the model domain (as a function of the grid resolution) from 2 days in the open sea and increasing, thus diminishing the restoration contribution, toward the coast. Therefore, the nudging allows the model state to be reconciled with the assimilated

MED-REA data in the open sea, limiting error growth in the simulation, and to fully compute the high-resolution hydrodynamics along the coast and in the coastal transitional environments (bays, deltas, estuaries and lagoons) (CMCC).

4. List of software repositories

Overview table of algorithms with links to repositories.

Table 4.1. List of software and algorithms

#	Software/ algorithm	Deliverable and/or Milestone #	Task # and main objective	Institution	Zenodo descriptor	Repository link
1	SRResNet	D6.2	T6.2.2 AI methods: Using AI to enhance forecast resolution/ computation time	Hereon	This repository is for downscaling physical fields using a super-resolution residual neural network	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15613952
2	Ensemble SRResNet	D6.2	T6.2.2 AI methods: Using AI to enhance forecast resolution/ computation time	Hereon	Initial version of Ensemble Super-Resolution Residual Network for spatial wave downscaling.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15613819
3	Multivariate linear regression	D6.2	T6.2.2 AI methods: Using AI to enhance forecast resolution/ computation time	Hereon	This repository is for downscaling physical fields using multivariate linear regression. Here the model is applied to downscale significant wave height (SWH) in the Black Sea using low-resolution data from ERA5 and high-resolution data from CMEMS. [https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2025.121100] Both self-variable downscaling from low-resolutoin	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15614086

#	Software/ algorithm	Deliverable and/or Milestone #	Task # and main objective	Institution	Zenodo descriptor	Repository link
					SWH and cross-variable downscaling from low-resolution wind fields are applied.	
4	ConvLSTM	D6.2/M6.3	T6.2.2 AI methods: Using AI to enhance forecast resolution/ computation time	Deltares	The purpose of this repository is to publish the scripts used to predict Suspended Particulate Matter fields from Delft3D-FM hydrodynamic data, using a ConvLSTM model setup.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15645941
5	4DVarNet - dLSTM	D6.1/M6.2	T6.1.2 Implementation of new nesting techniques	Deltares	This repository contains the training, testing and some pre/post processing scripts, used in the FOCCUS project, for D6.1. The purpose of this repository is to publish the scripts used to gap-fill weekly averaged SPM satellite observations (CMEMS), for 2011 until 2024.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15683195
6	3D DCSM-FM thermobaricity	D6.1/M6.2	T6.1.2 Implementation of new nesting techniques	Deltares	The attached scripts are proof of implementation for the integrated thermobaricity into the equation of state, in DFlow-FM. This work is part of D6.1. The thermobaricity attributions have been mostly made by Julien Groenenboom and	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690055

#	Software/algorithm	Deliverable and/or Milestone #	Task # and main objective	Institution	Zenodo descriptor	Repository link
					Harmen Wierenga, but the scripts themselves are a result of many more people, whose contributions can be further explored in the gitlab. Documentation of the thermobaricity implementation can be found in section 3.4.2 of the documentation, see related works.	
7	Super Resolution of SSH	D6.2	T6.2.2 AI Techniques	NERSC	First release containing a GAN to do super resolution on DUACS data by patches.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15614406
8	OceanVar	D6.2/M6.3	T6.3.1, Data assimilation in AdriFS	CMCC	N/A	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15624932
9	NEMO-to-CMEMS	D6.1/M6.2	T6.1.2, Implementation of new nesting capabilities	Shom	First pre-release dedicated to conversion of native NEMO model output to CMEMS-type data structure.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526387
10	Nudging in SHYFEM	D6.1/M6.2	T6.1.2, Implementation of new nesting capabilities	CNR	The repository contains the SHYFEM model code, which includes the routines for nudging the large-scale temperature and salinity fields.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1311736
11	ML-Calibration	D6.1/M6.2	T6.1.2, Implementation	Shom	Tools developed at Shom for the	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15537127

#	Software/algorithm	Deliverable and/or Milestone #	Task # and main objective	Institution	Zenodo descriptor	Repository link
			of new nesting capabilities		Tolosa-SW configuration in the Horizon Europe FOCCUS project (https://foccus-project.eu/)	
12	ensemble_wave	D6.2	T6.2.1 Ensemble technique	CMCC	This tool processes the ensemble members to provide hourly stochastic metrics for significant wave height and wave period from unstructured grid model.	https://zenodo.org/records/15637958
13	Boundary condition bias corrections	D6.1/M6.2	T6.1.2: Implementation of new nesting capabilities	MET.NO	Code related to WPs2 and 6 of the FOCCUS project from MET Norway. Data to the ocean models may be found on https://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog.html	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656700 (cf. https://github.com/metno/FOCCUS/coastal_system/boundary_conditions)
14	Observation operators	D6.2, M6.3	T6.3.1: Synergistic use of models and observations	MET.NO	Code related to WPs2 and 6 of the FOCCUS project from MET Norway. Data to the ocean models may be found on https://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog.html	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656700 (cf. https://github.com/metno/FOCCUS/data_assimilation/observations/operators)
15	Impact assessment	D6.2	T6.3.1: Synergistic use of models and observations	MET.NO	Code related to WPs2 and 6 of the FOCCUS project from MET Norway. Data to the ocean models may be found on https://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog.html	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656700 (cf. https://github.com/metno/FOCCUS/data_assimilation/impact)

#	Software/algorithm	Deliverable and/or Milestone #	Task # and main objective	Institution	Zenodo descriptor	Repository link
16	Observation error analysis	D6.2	T6.3.1: Synergistic use of models and observations	MET.NO	Code related to WPs2 and 6 of the FOCCUS project from MET Norway. Data to the ocean models may be found on https://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog.html	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656700 (cf. https://github.com/metno/FOCCUS/data_assimilation/observations/error_statistics)
17	Model diagnostics for freshwater dynamics	D6.2	T6.3.2: Land-ocean coupling and diagnostics	MET.NO	Code related to WPs2 and 6 of the FOCCUS project from MET Norway. Data to the ocean models may be found on https://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog.html	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656700 (cf. https://github.com/metno/FOCCUS/coastal_system/model_diagnostics)
18	Model diagnostics for currents and drift	D6.2	T6.3.2: Land-ocean coupling and diagnostics	MET.NO	Code related to WPs2 and 6 of the FOCCUS project from MET Norway. Data to the ocean models may be found on https://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog.html	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15656700 (cf. https://github.com/metno/FOCCUS/applications)
19	Observation analysis: Analysis 1hz, 5hz, and 20hz high-resolution Sea Surface Height satellite data	D6.2	T6.3.1: Synergistic use of models and observations	SOCIB		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15748211 /cf. https://gitlab.com/socib/foccus/-/blob/main/notebooks/Observation_analysis_stat.ipynb?ref_type=heads and https://gitlab.com/socib/foccus/-/blob/main/notebooks/Observation_analysis_wavenumber_power_spectral.ipynb?ref_type=heads)

#	Software/algorithm	Deliverable and/or Milestone #	Task # and main objective	Institution	Zenodo descriptor	Repository link
20	Model diagnostics for Sea Surface Height	D6.2	T6.3.1: Synergistic use of models and observations	SOCIB		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15748211 (cf. https://gitlab.com/socib/foccus/-/blob/main/notebooks/Model_diagnostics_for_Sea_Surface_Height.ipynb?ref_type=heads)
21	SHYFEM-MPI model tool for assessment of boundary forcing	D6.1/M6.2	T6.1.2: Implementation of new nesting capabilities	CMCC	This Jupyter notebook presents the Total Kinetic Energy (TKE) from the Child (downscaled) ocean model simulation - computed with SHYFEM-MPI using Daily or Hourly boundary forcing - and compares to the TKE of the Parent model - derived from CMEMS (Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service) Mediterranean Sea Analysis products.	https://zenodo.org/records/15638365
22	2D Wave Spectra Forcing	D6.1/M6.2	Implementation of CMEMS-MCSC interface improvements	HEREON	This repository contains a Jupyter Notebook demonstrating how to generate 2D wave spectra inputs for the GCOAST-BS model system (SCHISM-WWM) using data from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS). This repository is related to the FOCCUS project, specifically Deliverable D6.1, and aims to	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690198

#	Software/algorithm	Deliverable and/or Milestone #	Task # and main objective	Institution	Zenodo descriptor	Repository link
					provide a standalone demonstration of the methods used in this deliverable.	
23	Multi-model ensemble wave prediction	D6.2	T6.2.1 Ensemble technique	DMI	Pan-European wave aggregation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15696952
24	Nudging CMEMS T/S to improve initial condition and forecast	D6.1/M6.2	T6.1.2: Implementation of new nesting capabilities	DMI	First release	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15696216
25	SST bias correction through Nudging	D6.1	T6.1.2 Implementation of new nesting capabilities	RBINS	The repository contains the North-Sea model setup, Fortran additions for SST nudging in COHERENS, and associated compile/run scripts. The source code of the model COHERENS v3.0 is available at : https://gitlab.naturalsciences.be/e/comod/coherens_v3 .	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15706316
26	MOHID-SWAN operational coupling	D6.1	T6 2.1 Ensemble technique	+ATLANTIC	Implementation of a one-way coupling system between the hydrodynamic model MOHID and	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15756032

#	Software/ algorithm	Deliverable and/or Milestone #	Task # and main objective	Institution	Zenodo descriptor	Repository link
					the wave model SWAN.	

5. References

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